

pH-metric Study on Lanthanide(III)-EDTA-D(+)-Saccharic Acid Equilibria

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Mai¹ reported the dissociation constants of D(+)-saccharic acid. Macarovici and Birou² made a potentiometric study on the complexes of D(+)-saccharic acid with Ti^{IV}, Zr^{IV} and Th^{IV}. Spacu *et al.*³ studied the conditions under which some lanthanide compounds are formed with D(+)-saccharic acid. Limaye and Saxena⁴ made a potentiometric study on the Ln(III)-EDTA-hydroxyacid ternary complexes involving malic, lactic, glycolic and gluconic acids. Moeller *et al.*⁵ reviewed the coordination chemistry of rare earth metal ions. The present communication describes determination of the formation constants of the Ln(III)-D(+)-saccharate and Ln(III)-EDTA-D(+)-saccharate complexes by pH-titration method at 25 ± 1° and 0.1 M ionic strength (NaClO₄).

Results and Discussion

In the first set of experiment (i.e. pH titrations with mixture nos. 1, 2 and 3), the metal-ligand ratio was maintained at 1:1. The values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL were calculated by the standard expressions⁶. The proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation curves were obtained by plotting \bar{n}_A and \bar{n}

against pH and pL respectively. The values of dissociation constants (K_2^H and K_1^H) of D(+)-saccharic acid were obtained from the formation curve, n_A vs pH and by pointwise calculation and linear plot method. These values agreed well with the K_2^H and K_1^H values reported earlier¹. The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. In the present experiment, the \bar{n} values did not exceed 1. Therefore, the values of stability constants ($\log K_1$) for the reaction $\text{Ln}^{3+} + \text{Sa}^{2-} \rightleftharpoons \text{LnSa}^+$, were obtained by the method of interpolation at various \bar{n} values and the mean values of $\log K_1$ are recorded in Table 1. During pH-titrations, insoluble compounds were obtained at the following pH for different metal ions : 3.3 (La^{III}), 3.12 (Ce^{III}), 3.11 (Pr^{III}), 3.05 (Nd^{III}), 3.01 (Sm^{III}), 2.92 (Eu^{III}), 2.90 (Gd^{III}), 2.95 (Tb^{III}), 3.03 (Dy^{III}), 3.01 (Ho^{III}), 3.22 (Er^{III}), 3.32 (Yb^{III}), 3.95 (Lu^{III}) and 3.48 (Y^{III}). These insoluble compounds on analysis were found to correspond to the general formula C₆H₈O₈Ln.6H₂O. Similar observation was also reported by Spacu *et al.*³.

Ln-EDTA-D(+)-saccharic acid system : In the second set of experiments, the metal : EDTA : D(+)-saccharic acid ratio was kept 1 : 1 : 1. The pH-titration curves for the Sm-

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR Ln-SACCHARATE AND Ln-EDTA-SACCHARATE COMPLEXES

Temp. = 25±1°, ionic strength = 0.1 M (NaClO₄)

(for D(+)-Saccharic acid : $K_2^H = 7.413 \times 10^{-4}$, $K_1^H = 5.754 \times 10^{-5}$)

Cation	$\log K_{\text{Ln-Sa}}^{\text{Ln}}$	$\log K_{\text{Ln-EDTA-Sa}}^{\text{Ln-EDTA}}$
Y ^{III}	4.60	4.19
La ^{III}	4.42	3.90
Ce ^{III}	4.45	3.97
Pr ^{III}	4.49	4.01
Nd ^{III}	4.53	4.05
Sr ^{III}	4.56	4.08
Eu ^{III}	4.60	4.05
Gd ^{III}	4.51	4.01
Tb ^{III}	4.54	4.08
Dy ^{III}	4.57	4.13
Ho ^{III}	4.60	4.17
Er ^{III}	4.64	4.21
Yb ^{III}	4.67	4.25
Lu ^{III}	4.68	4.30

*Limits of error in the constants : ± 0.03 and ± 0.05 in log units for the binary and ternary systems respectively.

Fig. 1. pH-titration curves for the 1:1 binary, Sm^{III}-Sa and 1:1:1 ternary, Sm^{III}-EDTA-Sa systems : (A) acid, (B) H₂Sa, (C) Sm^{III}-Sa, (D) Sm^{III}-EDTA and (E) Sm^{III}-EDTA-Sa.

EDTA-Sa system is shown in Fig. 1. The curves for other lanthanides showed similar nature. For the formation of ternary complexes the necessary conditions, like the formation of primary ligand complex, Ln-EDTA at low pH

and its stability at higher pH at which the combination of the secondary ligand with Ln-EDTA takes place were satisfied by choosing the secondary ligand in such a way that the stability of the Ln.Sa complex is much less than that of the primary complex Ln.EDTA. Thus the possibility of ligand displacement was excluded. The species present in solution were therefore Ln.EDTA and Ln.EDTA.Sa. The strong coordinating tendency and hexadentate nature of EDTA also eliminates the possibility of disproportionation of Ln.EDTA.Sa into Ln(EDTA)₂ and Ln(Sa)₂. The non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curve over the mixed complex curve⁷ and the non-appearance of precipitate during pH-titration indicates the formation of mixed ligand complexes.

The values of \bar{n}_{mix} and the free ligand exponent, P_{mix}^L , were calculated by using Irving-Rossotti pH-titration technique and its extension to ternary system⁸. The plots of $n_{\text{mix}}/L_{\text{mix}}$ vs L_{mix} were found to be smooth. This indicates the absence of protonated and polynuclear complexes⁴. The values of \bar{n}_{mix} were found to be less than 1 in each system. Therefore, the values of stability constants, $\log K_{\text{Ln.EDTA.Sa}}^{\text{Ln.EDTA}}$ were evaluated by the method of interpolation at various \bar{n}_{mix} values and the mean values are recorded in Table 1.

Lanthanide ions form normally ionic compounds. Therefore the Born relation, $E = Z^2/2r(1 - 1/D)$ should hold for energy change in complexation of a gaseous ion of charge Z and radius r in a medium of dielectric constant, D . Since this energy, E is directly related to the stability constant, the $\log K_1$ values should increase linearly with Z^2/r . It was observed that this simple relationship exists in the light rare earth region (i.e. La to Eu). This equation, however, did not work while the heavy rare earths were considered, supporting the earlier observations⁵.

The values of formation constants of the ternary complexes, Ln.EDTA.Sa, were found to be less than these of the Ln.Sa, binary complexes. This lowering in the values of constants of the ternary complexes is ascribed to the extra strain created due to the extension of the coordination number of the lanthanide ions to greater than six and the coulombic repulsion between the binary complex (Ln EDTA)⁻ and the incoming ligand Sa²⁻ as shown by the complexation reactions,

An expected trend of increase in the values of formation constant with the gradual decrease in ionic radii of the lanthanide ions with a break (minimum) at gadolinium was

observed. The position of yttrium with respect to its electrostatic model and magnitude of formation constants of its complexes were found between holmium and erbium in the lanthanide series.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The disodium salt of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid was used as primary ligand. D(+)-Saccharic acid was derived from the insoluble D(+)-calcium saccharate by ion-exchange method². Carbonate-free NaOH solution was used in pH-metric titrations. The carbonate content of NaOH was assessed by the reported method⁹. pH-metric titrations were performed in N₂ atmosphere at 25 ± 1° and 0.1 M ionic strength (NaClO₄) using an ECIL-5652 pH meter. The following sets of solutions for the 1 : 1 binary (mixtures 1, 2 and 3) and 1 · 1 · 1 ternary (mixtures 1, 2, 4 and 5) were prepared : (1) 0.02 M HClO₄ (curve-A), (2) 0.02 M HClO₄ + 0.005 M H₂Sa (curve-B), (3) 0.02 M HClO₄ + 0.005 M H₂Sa + 0.005 M Sm(NO₃)₃ (curve-C), (4) 0.02 M HClO₄ + 0.005 M Sm(NO₃)₃ + 0.005 M EDTA (curve-D) and (5) 0.02 M HClO₄ + 0.005 M Sm(NO₃)₃ + 0.005 M EDTA + 0.005 M H₂Sa (curve-E).

The initial volume in each case was kept at 50 ml by adding distilled water and the ionic strength maintained at 0.1 M by adding NaClO₄. These solutions were pH-metrically titrated by carbonate-free 0.1 M NaOH solution.

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